

Local Government Reforms as Instrument for National Development in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined local government reforms as instrument for national development in Nigeria using qualitative data that rely on content analysis of extant literature that supports the aim of establishing and reforming the local government as the third tier of government to act as a veritable instrument for national development in Nigeria. However, available empirical literature has argued that despite the important role of local government as the third tier of government and an instrument of development, there is a glaring evidence of serious inadequacies. They posit that the current state of Local Government in Nigeria is characterized by unbridled interference of the State Government which is quite dismal largely due to poor management of resources, lack of autonomy, inadequate local leadership among others. Thus, to realize fully the intended development using Local governments as instrument, Local governments should be democratized and adequate measures provided to check the siphoning tendencies of its managements.

KEYWORDS: *Local Government, National Development, Local Government Reforms*

INTRODUCTION

Change, it has often been said is the only permanent thing. This statement has found constant and easy approval in the various institutional reformations of Local Governments. When the militarily seized political power in 1966, it was confronted by the political problems of re-organizing the institution of local government so as to provide a clearly defined scope of authority, responsibility and functions while at the same time maintaining an effective central presence in the localities in order to be able to determine and; control the pace and quality of development largely initiated or generated at the local level (Oyediran & Gboyega, 1979). Since 1978, which witnessed the first major local government institutional reform, many other reforms have taken place in that level of government. These institutional reorganizations have had far-reaching effects on national development. Idike (2014) posits that local government and national development are fully interrelated and that local government is seen as a tool for the promotion of national consciousness and national integration. Its emphasis is political development which modernization theorists see as the breaking down of primordial loyalties and the transfer of such loyalties to the central and national government. The local government becomes a tool of nation building and national unity. It decongests the activities of the centre by locating such to the locality but in doing this, it brings the influence of the centre to the locality (Abutudu, 2011). This developmental process

helps to spread development across the nation. According to Oyedele, Osezua, Abdulkareem and Ishola (2017) the local government constitutes the most critical level of government in the move for a sustainable national development. Over the years, national development has been canvassed to take off from the grassroots as the local government is widely known as a vital instrument for rural transformation and machinery for effective delivery of socio-economic services to the people (Adeline, 2014; Otoghile & Edigin, 2011). Development is perceived as a multi-dimensional process involving the re-organization and re-orientation of entire economic and social systems. In addition to improvements in income and output, it typically involves radical changes in institutional, social and administrative structures, as well as in popular attitudes and sometimes even in customs and beliefs. Emphasizing the need to have a full grasp of the meaning of development Professor Dennis Goulet (1971) had postulated that "it matters little how much information we possess about development if we have not grasped its inner meaning." In this regard, there are at least three basic components or core values that serve as a conceptual basis of practical guideline for understanding the inner meaning of development. This paper focuses on the effects of local government reforms on national development in Nigeria. The following section will x-ray empirical studies of related literature and the various local government reform aimed at bringing the government close to the grass root.

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Related Empirical Studies

Adeyemi (2019) investigated Local Government Administration in Nigeria: A Historical Perspective using descriptive statistics and secondary data. The study found out that, the current state of Local Government in Nigeria is characterized by unbridled interference of the State Government. Abdullahi and Ahmad (2018) examined good governance and local government administration in Nigeria: An imperative for sustainable development. With the aid of qualitative instruments, the study argued that institutionalization of good governance is one of the best strategy for sustainable development at local level. It also posits the performance of local government as it relates to grass root development in the country is quite dismal largely due to poor management of resources, lack of autonomy, inadequate local leadership. Ikeanyibe (2018) examined the uniformity in local government system and the governance model in Nigeria. The study was a conceptual contradiction between a nationally uniform local government system as constitutionally provided in Nigeria, and, the principles of governance model that is presently believed to advance the course of service delivery in government. The paper argues that the straitjacketed constitutional provisions that require every state government to establish a patterned, uniform local government system, is conflict-generating, opposed to effective management and harnessing of local differences in a highly differentiated country like Nigeria, and averse to the multi-jurisdictional principle advocated by the proponents of the governance model. It posits that that contrary to the constitutional provisions on the nature of local government, which autonomy is not strongly protected by the constitution, the state governments should be allowed to determine the nature and structure of local governments in their domain to reduce the abuse of the local government system and entrench competitive local government practice. Eme, Idike and Onuigbo (2017) investigated South- East local governments & democracy in Nigeria by relying on content analysis of extant literature. Finding reveals that as a result poor understanding of the operation of the Constitution and excessive control by states, corruption and the flaws in the 1999 Constitution, they remained handicapped. Oyedele, Osezua, Abdulkareem and Ishola (2017) examined Local government administration and national development in Nigeria: challenges and prospects. The study adopted a conceptual approach through the use of secondary sources of data. It also relied on content analysis of extant literature to analyze the place of local government in National development. Findings from the study revealed that the local government has lost its footing in the developmental process due to unwarranted encroachment into the administration, finance and operations of the local government by the state governments. Nwofia (2017) examined due process in public procurement as anti-corruption strategy in Nigerian local government using ex-post facto research design to carry out an expository analysis of how corrupt officials steal Local Government funds and the implications for rural development. The study found that lack of due process in the system's procurement processes perpetuates corruption.

Akani (2017) carried out a theoretical appraisal of local government administration and how it has provoked grassroots development in Nigeria using descriptive statistics. The study discovered that the objective of the 1976 Local Government Reform has become a mirage. The

ruling class now sees it as a patrimony to satisfy political allies and cronies through the award of contracts and political appointment. Abdullateef, Oluyemi, Danjuma, Olatunji and Olawale (2017) examined local government reform and rural development as perceived by the people of Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State, Nigeria. The study relied on descriptive statistics and analysis. Findings from the study posits that overriding function of the state governments, lack of autonomy, corruption and embezzlement among others as the problems and challenges that have hindered its effective performance. It further revealed that that local governments have not been able to perform their functions adequately majorly due to lack of autonomy. Ebiziem and Obi (2015) carried out an appraisal of the autonomy of local government as a pre-condition for national development using documentary method of secondary sources of data collection and content analysis to examine the relationship of the three tiers with references to authority, finance, personnel, political and ecological relationship vis-à-vis social and economic development. Findings revealed that local government in Nigeria is not operating full autonomous status because of some limitations in the constitutional provision of its operation particularly in terms of its structure, composition, control, revenue and other administrative matters and this has greatly affected her optimal performance to the rural people. Okafor, Chukwuemeka and Udentia (2015) examined developmental local government as a model for grassroots socio-economic development in Nigeria. The study critically argued that the present system whereby, the Constitution gives the State governments the power to handle issues of organization and responsibility in the local governments places a strong limitation on local autonomy and governance at the local level. The abuse of these provisions in the constitution by the State governments coupled with other issues such as low level of commitment to the people and lack of monitoring and evaluation are negatively affecting grassroots socio-economic development in the Country. The study posits that a developmental local government model which has local economic development (LED) as 'the mandate' to address the concerns of poverty, unemployment and inadequate resources in the rural areas. The LED approach enables local governments to stimulate economic activities and improve the socio-economic conditions of people in the localities by working in partnership with private and other non-governmental sectors. Onodugo, Amujiri, Asogwa and Anyadike (2015) examined community development and local governments in Nigeria: A discourse. The study critically evaluated the role and challenges of local government in community development in Nigeria. The study found glaring evidence of serious inadequacies in basic social services and amenities to the rural community, emphasis in this regard has been placed on mobilization for sustainable community development. The study further revealed that local government plays a variety of roles to meet-up with the challenges of community development.

Idike (2014) carried out a study on local government and sustainable national development in Nigeria. The study relied on extensive literature to ascertain the opinions of various scholars in extant literature. Findings revealed that local governments in Nigeria have remained a mirage that have left much to be desired of the people. The study revealed that the negative national development in the Nigerian state is shown in the living standards of Nigerian

citizens, as different from abstract figures from Nigeria's officialdom and more recently, collaborated figures between the Nigerian sides and internationally recognized rating institutions that have constantly rated Nigeria among the poorest countries with most of its poor citizens living in the rural areas. Ibieta and Ndukwe (2014) examined local government administration in Nigeria and community development: the efficiency services interrogation. The study reliance on secondary data backed by practical observation and analytical framework. Findings revealed that the leading personnel, policy outcomes and political/administrative environments of local government administration in Nigeria (within the period of study) portrayed them as failed institutions. Adebayo (2014) examined local government and the challenges of rural development in Nigeria using secondary source in collection of data. The study posits that local governments were faced with such challenges like inadequate finance, corruption, poor implementation of projects, lack of competent manpower, high level of illiteracy, lack of due consultation and non-involvement of local dwellers in policy decisions and hijack of local government allocation by the state government.

Indeed the aim of establishing and reforming the local government as the third tier of government has been seen as a welcome development in extant literature. Available empirical literature has argued that despite the important role of local government as the third tier of government and an instrument of development glaring evidence of serious inadequacies. They posits that the current state of Local Government in Nigeria is characterized by unbridled interference of the State Government which is quite dismal largely due to poor management of resources, lack of autonomy, inadequate local leadership among others.

Local Government Reforms and National Development

In order to determine the development effects of local government institutional reforms on the nation, it may be sufficient to examine the previous local government systems and their defects. The origin of system of local administration in Nigeria could be traced to the system of indirect rule. When Lord Lugard established British authority in Northern Nigeria, "he was faced with an acute shortage of experienced officers to whom he could delegate authority and of money with which to employ them" (Price, 1967). Moreover, he found in existence strong and well organized indigenous states (emirates) in that area. Conscious of the fact that direct rule as practiced in the British crown colonies was not possible in the vast hinterland regions of the protectorate, Lugard preserved the emirates and used them as instruments of colonial rule, hi the decade that followed, he rationalized a system of local administration popularly known as indirect rule. It's essential features were the preservation of traditional political institutions and their adaptation, under the tutelage and direction of the British administration, to the requirements of modern units of local government (Coleman, 1958). When the Northern and Southern protectorate were amalgamated in 1914 and Lugard became its Governor-General he extended and adapted tins system to the Southern Provinces. With the Emirs as sole native authorities, and under the supervision of residents, the indirect rule system was very successful in the North, in the West, the Obas fitted reasonably well into the indirect rule pattern, hence the system was partially successful there. But

in the east, where traditional authority was diffused amongst Ibos, the system failed completely with the creation of artificial chiefs who abused the power invested on them. Thus local government systems in the north and south started developing separately from the earliest of times.

The outbreak of the Second World War, the close involvement of Nigeria in that war and the allied propaganda which emphasized democracy and the right of all peoples to choose whatever forms of government they would like to be under stimulated considerably political awakening in the country (Olusanya, 1980). The British, realizing that the war had let loose forces that could not be contained without some political concessions, granted political and constitutional concessions to the Nigerian nationalists. The first fruits of these concessions manifested late 1940 when Nigerians were given their first opportunity ever to actively participate in the formulation of the constitution, the Macpherson's Constitution of 1951, under which they were to be governed. Under Macpherson's Constitution of 1951, regions ceased to be mere administrative units and became political entities, each vested with both executive and legislative powers in respect of a specific area of the country. While the 1951 Constitution has been seen as "an important landmark in the history of Nigeria", (Oyediran & Gboyega, 1979). it unfortunately brought about increasing trend towards regionalism. One of the side effects of this was the widening disparate conditions in the local government systems in the country which were infused with and constrained by different philosophical conceptions of local government. In the South the governments of the East and West conceived of local government in extremely liberal terms which led to a rapid and unrestrained adoption of what they considered to be the essence of the British model of local government with its emphasis on popular participation. In the North a more conservative approach led to the adoption of a reform which emphasized functional effectiveness rather than popular participation (Oyediran & Gboyega, 1979).

The first efforts at reforms were led by the Eastern region which in 1950 replaced the Native Authority Ordinance by a local Government Ordinance. Under the former ordinance, a number of chiefs and elders were appointed by the government to form the native authority council of the area. The Local Government Ordinance of 1950 enabled the majority (80 percent) of the councillors to be directly elected. But the more important change related to political control... The keynote of that Ordinance was a change of management - the elimination of control by the administration which had been a feature of the former native authority system and vesting of power in virtually autonomous councils. In the Western region the Local Government reform took place in 1953 with the coming into effect of the Local Government Law 1952 in February 1953. As in the Eastern Region, political control of the Local Government councils shifted decisively to elected representatives who comprised three-quarters of the council memberships. An important outcome of these reforms in the Eastern and Western Regions was that the district officer was kept at a distance from council proceedings and administration; on giving notice in writing, he might visit the council to examine records, and liaise advice might be sought but it was at the discretion of the council to accept or reject (Oyediran & Gboyega, 1979).

In the Northern Region, on the other hand, the government was cautious, indeed tardy, in democratizing the local government system to enable it to embody the political purposes embraced by the Southern governments in the 1950's (Wraith, 1964). The native authority of 1954 only changed little of substance, merely consolidating existing arrangements, but it even retained the term 'native authority' which elsewhere had been discarded because it was regarded as pejorative (Cowan, 1958). These different philosophical conceptions of local government were to linger on until the military seized political power in 1966 and was confronted by the problem of re-organizing the institution of local government in the country, in practical terms, in the Southern Nigeria, the need was to revitalize and consolidate the local government system which had become the object of contempt while in the Northern Region, the need was to modernize the system by emphasizing popular participation and control and thereby diffusing the power of emirs and traditional rulers who tightly controlled the native authorities. The onset of military rule in 1966 marked the beginning of important changes in the system of local governance. However, it was not until the end of the civil war in 1970 that any serious effort was made by state governments to draw up plans for local government. In general, even though each state went its way, there appears to be three major directions of development, in the East Central, Rivers, South Eastern and Mid-Western States, local government in the form of local governance by elected councilors was abandoned in favour of the administration of local affairs by state officials, acting in consultation with local representatives. The Western state opted for a North American model of council managers in which the principal virtues are viability and efficiency but not democracy, in the Northern States, the emphasis was on increasing popular representation and weakening of the traditional hold on the functioning of local political institution.

Thus before the 1976 reforms, there was no local government in the country truly worthy of that name, since they were all suffering from a number of defects. As stated in the forward to the Guidelines for local Government Reform: "Local Governments have, over the years, suffered from the continuous witting down of their powers. The state governments have continued to encroach upon what would normally have been the exclusive preserves of Local Government. Lack of adequate funds and appropriate institutions had continued to make Local Government ineffective and ineffectual. Moreover, the staffing arrangements to ensure a virile local government system had been inadequate. Excessive politicking had made even modest progress impossible. Consequently, there has been a divorce between the people and government institutions at their most basic levels (Panter-Brick, 1978). It was in order to rectify these defects that the 1976 Local Government Reforms were embarked upon. Launching these Reforms, Shehu Musa Yar'Adua (1976) stated the main purpose of the Reforms when he said, "... the fundamental purpose of these reforms is to spread development to every corner of this country". While the Reforms were flexible enough to accommodate all shades of characteristics and local peculiarities, four basic criteria to be met by all local governments were spelt out (Ibid).

1. Local Governments must have definite and precise function designed to promote the development of the Local Government Area.

2. Local Governments must have assured finances to enable them plan their budgets and carry out their functions.
3. Local Governments must be adequately staffed with people of the right caliber.
4. The conditions of service must be such as to attract and keep these people in the service of Local Governments. While the Reforms were praised nationwide as a landmark in the history of local Government system in Nigeria and as a courageous decision at recognizing Local Governments as the third tier of governmental activity in the nation, the Reforms were not far-reaching enough to generate the desired development at local levels. The following bear this statement out: The Federal Military Government does not intend to impose any solutions of indeed any structure on the country at the Local government level. It accepts the principle that Local government is primarily the responsibility of State governments. It merely wishes to emphasize that these responsibilities should be clearly defined and that the Local Government should have adequate financial resources to meet their obligations which are mainly to stimulate development at the grassroots. (Panter-Brick: 254). But the disappearance of the Divisional Officer who had an all-pervading influence in the localities does not imply that the government will not supervise Local governments. The various state governments are to appoint Local Government Inspectors who have access to Local Government meetings and records in order to discharge the State Government's duties of oversight. In addition there is reserve power to dissolve any council which is judged not to have performed satisfactorily. The only limitation on this power is that a Management Committee appointed by a State government in place of a local council may not remain in place for more than three months or, if its authority is renewed, for more than one year in the aggregate. (Gboyega & Oyediran, 1978). For the first time since the introduction of popularly elected government councils in Nigeria, the federal government has allocated a large sum of money to ensure effective government at the grassroots... Yet these efforts need the positive support of state officials who have the basic responsibility for Local government. This is where the danger lies. Even if finance ceases to be a problem and qualified staff appointed and regularly trained, if state officials refuse to change their attitude all the federal government efforts will be in vain. From all available evidence, state officials still look at Local government as mere agents of state Government and of the State Civil Service (Ibid:268). The issue of status of Local government was considerably debated in the Constituent Assembly in 1977 and the Assembly was divided on the nature of Local government to be entrenched in the Constitution. The bone of contention was whether Local government should be given independent powers or be subject to State control. Those who felt Local government is the most important level of government, since it is the level closest to the people favoured its independence from state control. Alhaji Abubakar Rimi, former Governor of Kano State summed up their views when he argued: (proceedings of the Constituent Assembly, 1977:1994).

Local Government is the most important government of our land. The Local government is the nearest and most

immediate government to the man. The man in my village does not care about who the President of Nigeria is. He does not even care about who the Governor of Kano State is. He cares only about those who are Councillors and Chairman of his Local Government. We should go the whole hog and State the functions and the powers of the Chairman and even go to the extent of stating how to conduct Local Government elections. Others believe that if the structure and powers of Local government were too well defined in the constitution, this would make it extremely difficult to adjust the form of Local government to suit local needs and desires. At the end of the day, the provisions in the constitution concerning Local government reflected a compromise between those opposing positions. The Constitution assures the existence of Local government and sets forth a list of its functions or powers. However, both its existence and functions are to be provided for in a law enacted by State governments. Thus, during the Second Republic there was no improvements on the status of Local governments beyond the stipulations of 1976 Reforms and therefore state governments continued to use them as agents of state governments.

The Babangida Reforms

Launching the 1976 Local Government Reforms, Shehu Musa Yar'Adua stated the main purpose of the Reforms when he said "... the fundamental purpose of these reforms is to spread development to every corner of this country". The 1976 Reforms were not far-reaching enough to achieve its fundamental purpose. Local governments still had structural and operational problems which included financial incapacity, low executive capacity, lack of operational autonomy, inappropriate structures, poor quality of Councillors and undemocratisation of councils. The effect of these problems was poor performance of Local governments. It was during Babangida's regime that the most far-reaching reforms were made and directed towards the problems which had resulted in poor performance of Local governments over the years. These reforms were embodied in the Local Government (Basic Constitutional and Transitional Provision) Decree Number 15 of 1989 and its various amendments-decrees Number, 10 & 23 of 1991.

The Main Features of Babangida Reforms

5. Structure

Obviously, most of the Local Government Areas were so large that the local people could not feel their impact. The Babangida Administration tackled this problem by creating additional Local Government Areas. He almost doubled the number of Local Government Areas by creating a total of 287 Local government Areas thereby changing the number from 301 to 589. Abacha's Administration could have seen the wisdom in this and thus created additional Local Government Areas. Creation of additional Local Government Areas help to achieve a measure of relative balance in population and resources distribution.

6. Functions

The functions of Local governments as enshrined in the 1979 constitution were retained by the Babangida Administration. Considering the continued encroachment of state Governments on some of the money-yielding functions of the Local government, while making the 28th Independence Anniversary Speech, Babangida directed all State Governments to hands off with immediate effect, all the items of functions which were specified in section one of the Fourth Schedule of the 1979 Constitution which were

exclusive functions of Local governments. Following the directive, State Governments stopped encroaching on the functions which were exclusively allocated to local governments.

7. Finance

The Reform which the Babangida Administration made in the area of finance significantly strengthened the financial base of the Local government. As stated above, the administration stopped State Governments from encroaching on the revenue-yielding functions of Local governments. Secondly, the Administration increased the Local government's statutory share of the Federation Accounts from ten percent to twenty percent, resulting in tremendous increase in the financial resources of Local governments. Thirdly, in order to stop State Governments from diverting funds meant for Local governments as had been the practice, the Babangida Administration directed that the 20 percent of Local governments statutory allocated from the Federation Accounts should be paid directly to Local governments instead of through State Governments. Finally, for the purpose of promoting greater financial accountability in Local Governments, the Babangida Administration created a separate Office of Auditor-General for the Local Governments of a State. There are two reasons for this. Firstly, to enhance Local government autonomy. Secondly, to ensure that Local governments' accounts are promptly and efficiently audited, which would foster greater accountability and financial discipline.

Local Government Autonomy

This refers to the freedom of the Local government to appoint and discipline its own staff, make laws and policies, raise and manage its own finances, provide services within the range of its allocated functions and powers, and award contracts within the range of its resources and functions without interference. Before, the 1976 Reforms, Local Governments were creatures of the State Governments which were vested with the sole powers to make and unmake them. Consequently, Local governments were excessively controlled by their respective State Governments. Moreover, State Governments appointed, modified, dissolved and suspended Local Government Councils at will.

One of the objectives of the 1976 Local government Reform was to change that trend and make the Local government a third-tier of government with adequate autonomy. Unfortunately, the 1976 Reform did not achieve in practice the intended objectives. The Babangida Administration recognized and appreciated the negative effects of inadequate autonomy of Local governments in the discharge of their legitimate functions and took a number of far-reaching measures aimed at granting adequate autonomy to the Local governments including the scrapping of ministries of Local Governments in all the States of the Federation. Thus, Local Government became truly and no longer nominally, the third-tier of government. The independent existence of Local governments is now guaranteed, thereby making Nigeria truly a federal State with de-concentrated access to the political process in all levels of government.

The Presidential System

The 1979 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, provided for the presidential system of government for the Federal and State Governments. Local Governments

continued to operate the parliamentary system of government. In 1991, the Babangida Administration decided that Local Governments, like the Federal and State Governments, should operate the presidential system of government in line with their full status as the third-tier of government.

As a result of the Reform, Local Government Council became "properly constituted as the Legislative Arm of Local Government" and charged with law-making among other functions (Guidelines, 1991). Local Government Chairman became an Executive Chairman, and ceased to be a member of the Council just like the President of the Federation and Governors of States. In the same vein, supervisory chancellorship was abolished. The Constitutional Conference instituted by Abacha Administration had recommended that the various levels of Nigeria government, Federal, State and Local Governments should operate a system of government that should combine the features of presidential and parliamentary systems of government. Abacha Administration has accepted the recommendation and with this, supervisory chancellorship is back at local Governments. Local Government Chairman still remains an Executive Chairman, however.

Effects of the Reforms

The reforms have had both positive and negative effects. Positively, the intention of the reforms to make Local Governments the third-tier of governmental activity in the nation is a reality. State Governments no longer encroach on the money-yielding functions of Local Governments. Again, Local Governments Statutory Allocation from the Federation Accounts is now paid directly to them through any branch of the Central bank of Nigeria close to the concerned Local Government Areas. The benefit of this is that funds meant for Local governments are no longer diverted by State Governments. Moreover, through the reforms the statutory allocation of Local governments has been tremendously increased. Thus, strengthening the financial base of Local governments significantly.

Finally, right and well qualified caliber of staff that could manage properly the affairs of Local governments have been attracted to Local governments as a result of these reforms which created a forceful and dynamic Local government leadership system. The strengthening of Local governments by these reforms has had some negative effects, not originally intended. While a forceful leadership system, executive chairmanship, was provided at Local government to ensure unflinching attention in execution of approved policies and programmes and Local government financial base tremendously enhanced to provide adequate funds to activate development in Local governments, these have actually resulted in attraction of crooks and vultures in Local governments who mainly see Local governments as goldmine. These rogues are actually out to embezzle every available kobo in the Local government's treasury. The intention behind the reforms means little or nothing to them.

CONCLUSION

We have seen that before the 1976 Local Government Reforms, there was no Local government in the country truly worthy of that name. They were all suffering from a number of defects. The 1976 reform was not far-reaching enough to generate the intended development. The perennial problems

of Local government which included financial incapacity, low executive capacity, lack of operational autonomy, inappropriate structure and democratization of councils continued to exist. These resulted in poor performance of Local governments. The Babangida Reforms were directed towards the solution of these problems. In making the reforms, the Babangida Administration intended that Local governments must emerge as growth points and provide the much needed push to activate and energize productive activities in rural Nigeria and thus reverse the phenomenon of rural-urban drift. The administration believed, and rightly too, that it is through an effective system of Local government that the human and material resources of the local communities could be mobilized, exploited and utilized for massive rural transformation. To achieve this, the Babangida Administration made series of reforms in all facets of Local government including structural, functional, financial and administrative spheres. However, in a true Nigerian way, rogues of all kinds have been attracted by these noble objectives whose only stock in trade was to embezzle every penny found in the Local government treasury. Thus, to realize fully the intended development using Local governments as instrument, Local governments should be democratized and adequate measures provided to check the siphoning tendencies of its managements.

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